

Granulation of calcium phosphates based on principles of Leidenfrost effect

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INTRODUCTION: Calcium phosphates (CaPs) are an important class of biomaterials, that are widely used as bone substitutes, bone cements, coatings, and drug delivery systems. Crystalline CaPs - hydroxyapatite and tricalcium phosphates - have been extensively studied for the above-mentioned applications. Recently amorphous calcium phosphate (ACP) has regained researcher's interest due to its superior biocompatibility and resorbability when compared to crystalline CaPs. However, ACP is metastable, and it transforms into crystalline phase/s after contact with moisture and/or elevated temperatures. Therefore, use of conventional technologies for processing of ACP into applicable biomaterial forms is limited. Aim of the study was to investigate means of ACP's amorphous structure preservation throughout granulation process based on principles of Leidenfrost effect.

METHODS: ACP was synthesized based on rapid reprecipitation method [1]. Different concentrations (2-7 wt.%) of obtained ACP precipitates were resuspended in H₂O/EtOH mixtures (e.g., 50/50 vol.%) to find optimal suspension parameters for granule formation. Next, the ACP suspensions were dropped drop by drop onto a heated surface (> 200 °C). Evaporation of H₂O/EtOH should lead to granule formation based on Leidenfrost effect. Leidenfrost effect implies levitation of liquid or suspension droplets above a heated surface, where temperature of the surface is much higher than that of the liquid's boiling point. Obtained granules were characterized using SEM, XRD and FT-IR.

Furthermore, phase stability of the resuspended ACP was investigated in H₂O/EtOH mixtures up to 72 h by withdrawing samples for freeze-drying.

RESULTS: Granule formation technology based on principles of Leidenfrost effect led to granule formation with ACP concentration of 5 wt.%. Minimum EtOH amount was found to be 50 vol.%. Obtained granules had a dense and uniform surface (Fig. 1B). Use of 50:50 vol.% H₂O/EtOH mixture kept ACP in its amorphous state for at least 72 h compared to 8 h for ACP resuspended in H₂O alone.

Fig. 1: A) Schematics of the Leidenfrost effect. B) CaP granule prototype in SEM image.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS: Use of Leidenfrost effect for formation of ACP granules was investigated as potentially interesting technology, that has never been presented before for obtaining ACP granules. By adjusting suspension's ACP and EtOH concentrations it was possible to obtain ACP granules with preserved amorphous structure. Furthermore, the resuspension step in EtOH sped up the granulation process using principles of the Leidenfrost effect and allowed to extend overall processing window of ACP based materials as it preserves its structure for at least 72 h. However, the technology should be improved in terms of obtaining larger amounts of granules. Overall, this study widens potential of ACP to be used in the biomaterial field.

REFERENCES: ¹J. Vecstaudza et al (2016) *J Alloy Compd.* **700**:215-22.

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